

Appendix

Supplementary Table 1: Examples of proteins from the same family which had significantly different inter G box spacers

G protein family	Protein name	Organism	Inter G box spacer			
			Protein structure PDB ID	G1-G3	G3-G4	G4-G5
Translationa 1	Translation initiation factor IF-2	Bacillus stearothermophilus	1D1N;1Z9B;2 LKC;2LKD;2 NBG	46	54	34
Translationa 1	Eukaryotic translation initiation factor 5B (eIF-5B)	Saccharomyces cerevisiae	3WBI;3WBJ; 3WBK;4N3S; 4NCF;4V8Y;4 V8Z	64	54	66
Translationa 1	Peptide chain release factor 3 (RF 3)	Desulfovibrio vulgaris	3VQT;3VR1	68	54	115
Dynamin	Mitofusin-1	Homo sapiens	5GNR;5GNS; 5GNT;5GNU; 5GO4;5GOE; 5GOF;5GOM; 5YEW	96	59	47
Dynamin	Dynamin-1	Homo sapiens	1DYN;2DYN; 2X2E;2X2F;3 SNH;3ZYC;3 ZYS;4UUD;4 UUK;5D3Q;6 DLU;6DLV	98	69	28

Supplementary Figure 1: Comparison of predicted G domain boundaries (in all G protein families), before and after SMA-Step 3.

Supplementary Figure 2: Comparison of unique G boxes (in all G protein families) predicted before and after SMA-Step 3

Supplementary Figure 3: G protein family-specific G box motifs predicted using SMA3

Supplementary Figure 4. Significance testing of predicted G-domains. (A) Ras, (B) Era (C) translational families. X-axis=proteins sorted in the order of number of matches obtained; Y-axis= number of predicted G domains [in actual protein sequence (blue) and average of no. of G-domains identified after 50 shuffles (red)].

